

CHEMICAL CONTENT AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF HONEY

Keywords

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ABSTRACT

People choose honey, a natural substance, because it tastes good and gives the body power. Additionally, honey has been shown to provide a number of health benefits. The components in honey give it a variety of therapeutic properties. One food that has both low negative effects and strong therapeutic effects is honey. People enjoy this cuisine because it tastes sweet and is readily available. Honey is a convenient alternative therapy option because of the aforementioned characteristics. At the same time, the quantity and purity of honey's constituents determine its medicinal qualities. In order for people to prefer quality and safe honey, quality controls of honeys must be carried out.

INTRODUCTION

Honey is a natural product preferred by people for its deliciousness and giving strength to the body. It is also seen that honey has various therapeutic effects on the body. Studies have shown that honey reduces oxidative stress, kills, or prevents the growth of microorganisms, prevents, or kills the growth of viruses and parasites, reduces inflammation and edema, is antimutagenic and prevents tumor formation or growth. Honey is more preferable and easily accessible than products produced by aralar such as pollen, beeswax, bee venom, propolis, etc.¹ The color of honey also has a high effect when choosing honey. This color difference between honeys varies according to the sources where the pollen and nectars in the formation of honey are collected.² These color changes can also occur in a short time as a result of keeping the honey for a long time in storage or heat applications. In some studies, it was found that dark colored honeys contain more components than light colored honeys².

Honey content

Honey is formed by the conversion of nectar found in flowers into a sweet food by bees (*Apis mellifera*). It is known that naturally produced honey is a more beneficial product than sugar in terms of human health³. Honey mainly contains sugar (fructose and glucose) and different structures such as enzymes, amino acids, organic acids, carotenoids, vitamins, minerals and aromatic substances. The antioxidant feature of honey, which allows many changes to occur in the human body, is due to the high amount of flavonoids and phenolic acids it contains³. In addition to the substances mentioned, there are many enzymes in honey. The most abundant enzymes in honey are invertase, glucose oxidase and diastase enzymes, which are a mixture of α and β amylases. In addition to these, catalase and acid phosphatase enzymes are other enzymes detected in honey. Invertase enzyme is an α -glucosidase enzyme synthesized by bees and catalyzes the hydrolysis of sucrose in nectar into monosaccharides.

The role of honey's content in its therapeutic effect

Some components in honey's content are responsible for the therapeutic effect of honey. It was

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previously mentioned that the antioxidant properties of honey are due to phenolic acids and flavonoids. In addition to these compounds, components such as catalase, proteins, organic acids, ascorbic acid, amino acids^{4,5,6,7} and water-soluble vitamins⁸ also contribute to the formation and difference in the effect. According to research, the antimicrobial effect of honey in the body may be due mostly to the level of hydrogen peroxide, catalase, and glucose oxidase^{9,10,11}, while non-peroxide components such as lysozyme and phenolic substances also play a role in the formation of this effect^{12,13}.

The enzymes identified in honey so far are invertase, glucose oxidase, diastase, catalase and acid phosphatase^{14,15}. Glucose oxidase is another important enzyme found in honey and synthesized by bees. This enzyme is responsible for the antibiotic effect of honey due to the production of hydrogen peroxide and gluconic acid. When bees use the nectar they collect in honey production, the invertase enzyme they produce is responsible for the conversion of sucrose into simple sugars such as glucose and fructose¹⁶.

Diastase is a mixture of α and β amylases. Diastase enzyme is responsible for the conversion of starch, which is in the polysaccharide group, into small molecules with the help of water. Like other enzymes, it breaks down and undergoes denaturation by interacting with heat. Another feature is that differences in enzyme activity may occur during accumulation. Considering this feature, differences in enzyme activity allow the determination of whether additives have been added to the honey or whether heat treatment has been applied by reducing the amount of enzyme¹⁷.

Changes made to honey

Honey is a food that can be subject to various tricks due to its preferability and easy availability. Honey produced with nectar collected by bees from flowers and does not contain any foreign substances is called Pure honey. Some honey producers also obtain honey by using various sugar syrups to increase the amount of the product formed¹⁸. In today's situation, honey obtained in this way has become a problem that needs to be paid attention to. Bees fed from various sugar syrups (such as glucose syrup, sucrose syrup) placed near honey hives are fed from nearby sugar syrups instead of feeding from nectars in flowers and they produce honey with changed pure content¹⁹. These honeys do not contain chemical substances produced by flowers in nature, this situation changes the effect of honey on the body. Because the therapeutic effects of honey on the body

are realized through the components in honey.

Therapeutic effect of honey

Honey has been preferred as a treatment in most societies from the past to the present. In the sources written by Dioscorides, it is thought that honey has cured wound infections for more than 2000 years. This idea continues today and it is thought that its effect has expanded even more^{20,21,22}.

The effect of honey on wound healing

For many years, honey has been used considering its therapeutic properties, and among these properties, eliminating infections in wounds has an important place^{23,34,35}. Honey is used in ulcers, inflammations of wounds caused by burns, and in healing regional wounds in bedridden patients^{26,27}. Honey reduces the infection in the wound and helps eliminate the edema in that area^{28,29}. In an experiment conducted to observe the treatment of honey on wounds, honey was used in the dressing of an infected wound. As a result of the study, it was determined that the surface of the wound was sterile for 3 to 10 days³⁰. In another study, dressings containing honey were applied to eliminate infection in wounds that occurred after cesarean delivery and to heal the wound more quickly. It was observed that the wound healed faster after the procedure and the infection caused by bacteria was eliminated rapidly, and the hospital stay of the patients was shortened³¹. At the same time, thanks to honey, the closure of open wounds with epithelial tissue and the formation of new connective tissue during healing in this area increased^{32,33}.

In the treatment of wounds, the area around the wound surface should also be clean. Various microorganisms may be present on the wound surface and this affects the healing time. Therefore, the wounded surface should be sterilized as much as possible. Honey is also used to eliminate the effects of many microorganisms. These microorganisms are bacteria and parasites. In addition to microorganisms, it is also effective on fungi and viruses^{33,34,35}. If we give an example of the antimicrobial property of honey, a 10% honey solution started to kill *Ecinococcus granulosus* in the 3rd minute³⁶. In skin transplantation performed to treat leg ulcers, it is observed that infections caused by some bacterial species negatively affect the procedure³⁷. It has also been found that honey is effective against the Rubella virus *in vitro*³⁸. It is thought that honey can be used in addition to drugs in the treatment of infected

wounds where antibiotic-resistant bacteria are observed³⁹. These properties of honey are the result of specific properties such as high osmolarity, low water effect, low pH and H₂O₂ formation due to the presence of sugar concentration^{40,41,42}.

In addition to these features, it is also necessary to mention the harm of honey use. The nectars collected by bees to create honey may contain microorganisms that are likely to be found in the environment and on plant surfaces. One of these microorganisms, *Cl. botulinum* spores, do not cause a problem in adults, but can cause problems in children under one year old. The spores of these microorganisms can multiply in honey, but they do not cause toxic effects. Since the intestinal flora of babies under one year old is not resistant to the spores of this microorganism, these spores cause toxic effects. As a result of this toxic effect, the inability to hold the head steady, body malaise and delayed reflex movements can be seen. Although it takes time to treat these effects, these effects are not seen afterwards. Although the possibility of these physiological disorders is very low, it is not preferred to give honey to babies under one year old^{41,42}.

Antimutagenic effect

Honey used orally increases the immunological effect, and it has been shown to have the ability to prevent the formation and spread of cancer, which is a disease of our age^{35,43}. As a result of testing honeys from 7 different producers in vitro, it was seen that the mutagenicity of Trp-p-1 was prevented⁴⁷. Honey was given to the experimental animals every day for 10 days before the tumors developed for the purpose of testing were given to them. After this process, it was determined that the tumor cells did not spread in the experimental animals³³.

Antioxidant effect

Oxidants are reactive compounds such as oxygen and are antioxidants found in many food products and the body and play a role in eliminating damage in the body⁴⁰. Oxidants form components such as free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can destroy cellular structures. These compounds interact with lipids, protein structures, enzymes and DNA in cell membranes. The reactions that occur as a result of this interaction damage the body and cause different diseases. Antioxidants help eliminate the free radicals that cause these events without showing their effects. Both enzymatic

substances and substances that are not formed by enzymatic reactions can act as antioxidants⁴¹. The antioxidant properties of honey generally depend on the color of the honey; darker honey tends to have higher antioxidant content. Phenolic compounds are the main source of the antioxidant activity of honey and the level of these compounds is related to the free radical absorption values of the honey⁷. Studies have shown that not only phenolic compounds but also the combination of different components in honey have antioxidant properties. Therefore, honey is an antioxidant that can be taken with diet⁷.

CONCLUSION

As a result, honey has various therapeutic effects thanks to the components in it. Honey is a food with high therapeutic effects and low side effects. Being a sweet food in terms of taste and being easily available helps people prefer it. These mentioned features make it convenient to use honey as an alternative treatment method. At the same time, the therapeutic properties of honey depend on the purity and quantity of the components in it. In this case, the preferred honeys must be of good quality. In order for people to prefer quality and safe honey, quality controls of honeys must be carried out. I think that studies in this area should be increased.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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No

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